

The Impact of Teacher Feedback and Motivation on Students' Academic Performance in Higher Secondary Education: A Study in District Nushki Balochistan

Journal of Quranic
and Social Studies
49-62

Ghazala Mengal

MPhil Education Research Scholar, Institute of Education
and Research, University of Balochistan, Quetta.

© The Author (s) 2025
Volume:5, Issue:2, 2025
DOI:10.5281/zenodo.

www.jqss.org

ISSN: E/ 2790-5640

ISSN: P/ 2790-5632

Dr. Abdul Nasir Kiazai

Director, institute of Education and Research
University of Balochistan, Quetta.

OJS **PKP**
OPEN JOURNAL SYSTEMS PUBLIC KNOWLEDGE PROJECT

Dr. Muhammad Zakir

Lecturer, Department of Sociology, University of Balochistan, Quetta

Abstract

The impact of teacher motivation and feedback on higher secondary level college levels students in District Nushki, Baluchistan's academic performance were investigated in this study. The main objectives of this study was to investigate the relationship between teacher motivation and student academic performance in higher secondary education settings and to understand the perception of students about teacher's feedback and motivation and influence on their motivation to improve academic learning. And had many significance as it addresses the vital role of teacher feedback and motivation aspects in improving students' academic performance in higher secondary education in District Nushki. Data were collected via a self-constructed questionnaire given to a random sample of 83 teachers and 241 students. Data analysis was done using the IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27. Descriptive statistics were used to characterize the demographic profile and variables; Regression analysis were employed to investigate correlations among the variables. The results demonstrated a good and statistically significant correlation between student performance, teacher motivation, and teacher feedback. Although the degree of correlation was little, results indicate that students are more probable to do better academically when their teachers are motivated and provide them feedback and helping them in their learning process. These results support earlier studies and point out how crucial teacher-centered techniques are for raising academic results.

Keywords: Teacher Motivation, Teacher Feedback, Student Academic Performance, Higher Secondary Education.